

Kaniadakis Distribution and $e/T \ll 1$ Considerations Part 2

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In Part I, we considered an approach to finding the Kaniadakis distribution $\exp(e_i/T)$ through $e/T \ll 1$ considerations which focused on seeking a second order correction to an exponential, $\exp(-e_i/T) = 1 - e_i/T + 5 (e_i/T)(e_i/T) + \dots$

Here we revisit the reasons for considering a power distribution in the first place, which in the Tsallis case ($q=$) yields a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. This leads to a solution: $\exp_q(x) = \{ 1 + (1-q)x \}^{\text{power } 1/(1-q)}$ ((1)). We note that for $q \rightarrow 1$, $1-q$ is tiny and $1+(1-q)x$ approximates an exponential (MB). The same condition, however, holds for $x=e_i/T \ll 1$, as we discussed in a previous note, and so, we argue, that this justifies a consideration of $e_i/T \ll 1$.

The point we wish to make here is that ((1)) is not only a solution of: $1/(1-q) \{ \exp_q(x)^{\text{power } 1/(1-q)-1} \}$, but also of $1/(q-1) \{ \exp_q(x)^{\text{power } 1/(q-1)-1} \}$ for $|x| \ll 1$. In other words, $\exp_q(x)$ for the $|x| \ll 1$ case is a solution to two $\ln_q(x)$ expressions. If one writes $k=1-q$, then for a fixed k , the two q values involved are $1-k$ and $1+k$. Thus, one may actually combine two different q value Tsallis $\ln_q(x)$ functions and divide by 2 to obtain an expression which has a single $\exp_q(x)$ solution for $|x| \ll 1$. When $|x|$ is larger, there is still a single solution, but it differs from $\exp_q(x)$. In other words, a sum of two Tsallis $\ln_q(x)$ yields the Kaniadakis $\ln_k(x)$ such that for $k \rightarrow 0$, one has $\ln_k(x) = \ln(x)$ and $\exp_k(x) = \exp(x)$.

Thus, one obtains the Kaniadakis distribution, but there are some fundamental differences between it and Shannon and Tsallis cases. The two latter create entropy as an average of information. In the Shannon case, information is $\ln(p)$ and this is averaged over p which is also used to average energy. In the Tsallis case, information is $\ln_q(p)$ and it is averaged over $p^{\text{power } q}$ as this probability is used to average e_i (energy). In the Kaniadakis case, entropy is obtained by integrating $\ln_k(p)$ over dp , where $\ln_k(p) = -e_i/T$ (or in (1) $-1/T (e_i-u)$ where u is the chemical potential). Then, an extremization process d/dp simply returns $\ln_k(p)$ which matches $-1/T (e_i-u)$ through two constraints.

We note that the Kaniadakis $\ln_k(p)$ case is the sum: $.5 \{ \ln_{q1}(p) + \ln_{q2}(p) \}$. For $q1 \rightarrow 1$ and $q2 \rightarrow 1$, this becomes: $\ln(\sqrt{pp})$. The $q1$ and $q2$ Tsallis cases involve probabilities $p^{\text{power } q1}$ and $p^{\text{power } q2}$, where $q1=1-k$ and $q2=1+k$. Taking $\sqrt{p^{\text{power } q1} p^{\text{power } q2}} = p$, which is the probability used to average e_i in the Kaniadakis case.

Power Law Considerations

The well-known Maxwell-Boltzmann solution, $\exp(-e_i/T)$ drops off as an exponential and is 1 for $e_i/T=0$. If one wishes to have a power law drop-off with a single parameter, one might consider that for large e_i/T one has $e_i/T^{\text{power } k}$, but for $e_i/T=0$, 1. A simple solution is:

$$(1 - e_i/T)^{\text{power } k} \quad ((2))$$

One sees that both large e_i/T and tiny e_i/T considerations apply. Furthermore, one may see that $1-e_i/T$ becomes $\exp(-e_i/T)$. To remove k , one may use:

$$(1 - (1/k) e^{i/T})^{\text{power } k} \quad ((3))$$

Writing: $k = 1/(1-q)$, yields the Tsallis distribution:

$$p(e_i) = \{ 1 - (1-q) e^{i/T} \}^{\text{power } 1/(1-q)} \quad ((4)) \quad (\text{unnormalized})$$

If one seeks a function $F(p) = -e^{i/T}$ (p is unnormalized), then the well-known solution is:

$$\ln_q(p) = 1/(1-q) \{ p^{\text{power } (1-q)} - 1 \} \text{ such that } q \rightarrow 1 \text{ yields } \ln_q(p) = \ln(p) \quad ((5))$$

At this point, one might mistakenly consider the problem of a power law distribution closed, but since we have argued that $e^{i/T} \ll 1$ considerations are important, we show, in the next section, that the solution ((4)) which is linked with ((5)) exactly is also linked to a $\ln_q(p)$ for a different q value in the $e^{i/T} \ll 1$ limit. This suggests that a combination of ((5)) for two q values may also yield a unique probability distribution which also becomes $\exp(-e^{i/T})$ in the particular limit of a parameter. We suggest that this is one way of seeing the Kaniadakis distribution emerge.

Small $e^{i/T}$ considerations

We take ((4)) and write $1-q = k$, i.e. $p(e) = \{ 1 - ke^{i/T} \}^{\text{power } 1/k} \quad ((6))$

This satisfies ((5)) $\ln_q(p) = 1/k \{ p^{\text{power } k} - 1 \}$, but in the $e^{i/T} \ll 1$ limit, it also satisfies, to first order:

$$1/(-k) \{ p^{\text{power } (-k)} - 1 \} \quad ((7))$$

As a result, the solution to $\ln_{q_1}(p(e_i, q_1)) = -e^{i/T}$ for q_1 satisfies $\ln_{q_2}(p(e_i, q_1)) = -e^{i/T}$ for $e^{i/T} \ll 1$, keeping only first order terms. The two values of q are:

$$q_1 = 1-k \quad \text{and} \quad q_2 = 1+k \quad ((8))$$

In the low $e^{i/T}$ limit a single $p(e_i)$ distribution satisfies two $\ln_q(p) = -e^{i/T}$ equations and one may average the two, i.e.

$$1/(2k) \{ p^{\text{power } k} - p^{\text{power } -k} \} = -e^{i/T} \quad ((9)) \quad \text{in the } e^{i/T} \ll 1 \text{ limit}$$

In the limit $k \rightarrow 0$, this function becomes $\ln(p)$.

The next question to ask is: Is there a solution if $e^{i/T}$ is no longer small? In such a case, ((9)) holds for any $e^{i/T}$ and the solution is well-known, it is the Kaniadakis:

$$\exp(-e^{i/T}) = \{ \sqrt{1 + k e^{i/T}} - k e^{i/T} \}^{\text{power } 1/k} \quad ((10))$$

In the $k \rightarrow 0$ limit this becomes the MB $\exp(-e^{i/T})$.

Thus, what seemed like a single power law solution (Tsallis case) has now led to a possible second formalism, namely that of Kaniadakis.

Entropy Considerations

We wish to compare entropy forms for the Shannon, Tsallis and Kaniadakis cases. There is a strong link between the Shannon and Tsallis cases and a weaker one with the Kaniadakis one. First, we stress that all three approaches have an $F(p(e_i)) =$ information such that:

$$F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad ((11)) \quad \text{Here } p(e_i) \text{ is unnormalized.}$$

A fundamental difference, however, occurs when one considers the notion of the average of information $F(p(e_i))$. In the Shannon and Tsallis cases:

$$S(\text{Shannon}) = - \sum \text{over } i \ p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) \quad \text{where } F(p) = \ln(P) \text{ and } p(e_i) \text{ is the probability used to average } e_i \quad ((12a))$$

$$S(\text{Tsallis}) = - \sum \text{over } i \ p(e_i)^q \ln_q(p(e_i)), \quad \text{where } F(p) = \ln_q(p) \text{ and } p(e_i)^q \text{ is the probability used to average } e_i. \quad ((12b))$$

In the Kaniadakis case: $S(\text{Kaniadakis}) = \int dp \ln_k(p)$ ((12c)) and so is not average information where $F(p) = \ln_k(p)$. In the Kaniadakis case, $p(e_i)$ is considered the probability needed to average e_i .

A question which arises is the following. In the Tsallis case, $p(e_i)^q$ is the probability needed to average e_i . The Kaniadakis case was created above using two q values, $q_1=1-k$ and $q_2=1+k$, meaning that there would be two e_i averaging Tsallis probabilities $p(e_i)^{1+k}$ and $p(e_i)^{1-k}$. Combining the two $\ln_q(p)$ functions to create a single one in k , with a single $\exp(-e_i/T)$ solution means that one is no longer distinguishing between the two Tsallis q \ln_q functions.

It is as if one performs instead of \sqrt{pp} :

$$\sqrt{p^{1+k} p^{1-k}} = p \quad ((13))$$

We note that this is keeping with the sum of the two Tsallis $\ln_q(p)$ functions, one with $q=1+k$ and the other with $q=1-k$.

In such a case: $\frac{1}{2} (\ln_q(p, q=1+k) + \ln_q(p, q=1-k))$.

In the $k=0$ limit this is like $\frac{1}{2} \ln(pp) = \ln(\sqrt{pp})$., used in ((13)).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider the Tsallis power law for $e_i/T \ll 1$ and note that in this case, $\exp_q(-e_i/T)$ is a solution of two q values, namely $1+k$ and $1-k$. In other words, one may write a sum of these two \ln_q functions multiplied by $1/2$ which has a single probability distribution solution for $e_i/T \ll 1$. For e_i/T non-tiny, one has the Kaniadakis solution $\exp_k(-e_i/T)$. We note that the sum of two $\ln_q(p)$ functions divided by 2, in the $k \rightarrow 0$ limit is equivalent to: $\ln(\sqrt{pq})$. In other words, the sum of two \ln_q 's is like considering the sqrt of the product of the two Tsallis q_1, q_2 probabilities used for averaging e_i : $\sqrt{p^{1+k} p^{1-k}} = p$ and so p is used for averaging e_i in the Kaniadakis case.

In the Shannon and Tsallis cases, entropy is $-\sum_i (probability\ used\ for\ averaging\ e_i) * \ln(\text{probability})$, while in the Kaniadakis case: entropy = $-\int dp \ln_k(p)$. (Here information = $\ln_k(p)$.) Thus, there is a difference between the Shannon and Tsallis case and the Kaniadakis one, even though all three have: information = $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$.

References

1. Kaniadakis, G. Non-linear Kinetics Underlying Generalized Statistics (2018)
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